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Government Policies and Their Impact on Life Expectancy in Pakistan: Analyzing Socio-Economic and Environmental Influences

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ABSTRACT

Life expectancy is a key indicator used to gauge the overall health and well-being of a population. This study investigates the impact of environmental, economic, and social factors on life expectancy in Pakistan, using time series data from 1990 to 2022. The objective is to examine how several crucial variables, such as healthcare expenditures, the number of physicians, educational attainment, GDP, emissions from fossil fuels, and carbon dioxide emissions, affect life expectancy. The study employs the ARDL-Bounds testing approach to measure how these variables predict life expectancy, providing insights into the intricate relationships between a country's public health, environmental policy, economic growth, and overall population lifespan. The findings indicate that GDP, healthcare spending, the number of physicians, and educational attainment positively impact life expectancy, while carbon dioxide and fossil fuel emissions negatively impact it. The study concludes that the government should promote economic growth, increase access to medical professionals, and enhance public health and life expectancy. Recommendations include increasing investments in healthcare and education. By pursuing these strategies, policymakers can reduce environmental risks and effectively increase life expectancy. It is essential to implement strict environmental regulations to minimize harmful emissions from fossil fuels and CO₂. An integrated strategy that promotes social, environmental, and economic well-being can achieve longer life expectancy and improved public health.

Keywords: Life Expectancy; GDP growth; Physicians; CO₂ emissions; Fossil Fuel Energy; Education expenditures; Healthcare expenditures; Pakistan.

1. INTRODUCTION

Life expectancy is usually considered the average number of years that an individual or population is expected to live from birth. It is a widely used measure in demography, public health, and social sciences to analyze health and mortality trends. Policymakers' foremost priority in the modern period is to combine strong economic growth with improved standards of living. Historically, global economic development has occurred at a faster pace in nations with greater growth rates. For these reasons, the relevant parties—politicians and governing bodies, among others—are assembling the strongest plans for advancing economic expansion in their nations (Wang et al., 2020).

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The significance of life expectancy lies in its ability to boost labor force productivity and ultimately contribute to higher rates of economic growth in the long run. Life expectancy has a significant impact on people's productive health and long-term economic outcomes (Alam et al., 2016). It has a well-recognized effect on healthcare determinants and economic growth at the individual level. From a theoretical standpoint, there are several ways in which life expectancy influences economic growth. Bloom et al. (2000) noted that life expectancy decreases with decreasing per capita GDP. However, a study revealed that after a nation reaches a certain wealth threshold, factors like rising per capita GDP are no longer linked to longer life expectancies. The use of fossil fuels for energy can indirectly affect life expectancy in several ways, mainly by contributing to air pollution and climate change. Industries that use fossil fuel energy run the risk of causing harm to human health, incurring future climate change expenses, and creating other environmental problems, all of which are seen as national security risks. However, nations, particularly those in resource-rich areas, use fossil fuels to ensure that production continues, electricity is generated, and reliable transportation infrastructure is maintained (Machol et al., 2013). Air pollution and climate change caused by fossil fuels are already seriously endangering people's health and wellbeing (Nadeau et al., 2022). The average surface temperature of the Earth has risen by roughly 1.1 °C since pre-industrial periods, mostly due to emissions from fossil fuels over the past century (Perera et al., 2020). The primary way that carbon dioxide (CO₂) affects life expectancy is through its role in causing climate change. As a significant greenhouse gas, CO₂'s rising atmospheric concentration has numerous unintended consequences for human health and welfare. CO₂ is the primary gas causing climate change, and its health implications have attracted the attention of many academics. The IPCC (2018) demonstrated that there is a correlation between CO₂ emissions and human health in the top 10 emitting nations from 1991 to 2014. Any rise in carbon emissions has a significant influence on infant mortality, as shown by research on the relationship between energy use and infant mortality in Africa (Wang et al., 2019). Kotcher et al. (2019) also highlighted this point. Currently, the widespread consensus is that carbon dioxide emissions are influenced by per capita GDP. However, the relationship between population and carbon dioxide emissions is complicated, and factors other than per capita GDP also impact carbon dioxide emissions. According to research by Mohammed et al. (2017), carbon dioxide emissions are influenced by population density. Physician density and LEB (Life Expectancy at Birth) are correlated, and this link is true whether or not economic affluence, urbanization, obesity, and other factors compete with one another. The strongest factor influencing LEB is physician density, followed by economic affluence. Smith, H. (2009) The two main practitioner groups in the healthcare workforce, nurses and doctors, have made significant contributions to lowering mortality and morbidity rates and improving general population health. As a result, physician density has been shown to significantly affect birth weight life expectancy worldwide, particularly in developing nations. The established potential confounders of economic affluence, urbanization, obesity, and other factors do not affect this contributory effect. The universal correlations between physician density and life expectancy within country groupings may confirm that the impact of a physician shortage is a worldwide issue (You & Donnelly, 2022).

Society is greatly supported by education on all fronts. This means that every type of investment needs to be considered when assessing economic growth. Belief and motivation for education to set higher standards are necessary for promising development in all areas of life. Ultimately, education is a crucial component of a country that fosters economic prosperity (Goczek et al., 2021). An increase in life expectancy should lead to sizable increases in optimal schooling and sizable reductions in total fertility, but only after the onset of the demographic transition, when life expectancy is sufficiently high. During the early stages of the transition, population growth should rise in tandem with life expectancy and subsequently slow down once it begins (Cervellati & Sunde, 2015). Life expectancy can be significantly impacted by health spending, particularly given the role that healthcare resources and services play in improving the general health of the populace. Higher health spending is typically linked to increased access to healthcare services, higher-quality healthcare, lower death rates, and the capacity to address socioeconomic factors that affect health outcomes. Empirical data from several Middle East and North Africa (MENA) nations demonstrate a direct correlation between efficient healthcare spending and increased life expectancy (Akinici et al., 2014). The overall amount spent on health care, accounting for both public and private sources, is determined by dividing the total amount by the country's population.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

There are three sections in this literature review. It begins by reviewing the literature to determine how life expectancy is affected by GDP per capita and health expenditure. The second section reviews the literature on how life expectancy is affected by education and the number of physicians. The third section examines the research on how emissions from fossil fuels and carbon dioxide affect life expectancy.

2.1. Impact of GDP per capita and health expenditure on Life Expectancy

Previous studies have continuously demonstrated a significant relationship between life expectancy and GDP per capita. Longer life expectancies are generally correlated with higher GDP per capita. Numerous variables contribute to this link. First, countries with higher GDP per capita often have superior healthcare infrastructures. Wealthier countries have easier access to medical facilities, qualified healthcare personnel, and advanced technologies for diagnosis and treatment. Additionally, the impact of health expenditure on life expectancy is significant. Research indicates that a higher health budget is associated with better health outcomes and, consequently, longer life expectancies. Greater access to preventative care, such as immunizations and screenings, which can identify and treat health disorders before they worsen, is made possible by higher health spending (Polcyn et al., 2023). This study examines the effects of health expenditure, energy consumption, CO₂ emissions, population size, and income on health outcomes in 46 Asian nations between 1997 and 2019. The study suggests that higher rates of energy use and healthcare spending eventually lead to better health outcomes for Asian nations. Among all the factors, spending on healthcare has the most significant impact on life expectancy in these nations. Therefore, Asian countries must take necessary steps to increase health spending, energy consumption, and long-term

economic growth to enhance health outcomes. Additionally, reducing CO₂ emissions is crucial for achieving the best possible health results. Osei-Kusi et al. (2024) determine the linear effects of economic growth on carbon emissions and their impact on mortality and morbidity rates in specific regions, including sub-Saharan Africa, the Middle East and North Africa, and Europe and Central Asia (SSA, MENA, ECA). The study examines the links between energy consumption, per capita GDP, life expectancy, and carbon emissions using longitudinal data from 82 panels collected over a 30-year period. The findings indicate that life expectancy, energy consumption, and carbon output are positively correlated in both the overall sample and specific regions. In most regions and models examined, analysis shows a positive association between GDP per capita and both carbon emissions and life expectancy. This highlights the significance of supporting sustainable development in a nuanced manner that considers the distinct economic and environmental challenges faced by different parts of the world. Younas & Younas (2024) aimed to evaluate the relationship between per capita GDP, gender-based literacy rates, and school life expectancy. The study approach is described in detail, including each step of instrumental growth and expansion, and the benefits and drawbacks of the selected strategy. The results suggest that differences in per capita GDP did not have a significant effect on gender-specific literacy or educational duration, as the regression models used did not find statistical relevance in per capita GDP. Saad (2024) investigated factors determining women's life expectancy at birth, including demographic, social, and economic factors such as adult mortality rate, total fertility rate, education, and GDP per capita. Using the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM), the study found that women's life expectancy in Saudi Arabia will rise over time. The fertility rate has a long-term, positive, and significant impact on women's life expectancy, while GDP per capita has a positive short-term impact but a negative long-term impact. Azam et al. (2022) examined factors affecting life expectancy in Pakistan from 1975 to 2020, focusing on the impact of environmental degradation measured by CO₂ emissions. Long-term estimates suggest that life expectancy is negatively impacted by CO₂ emissions and the death rate, while positively impacted by per capita income, birth rate, health spending, and education. The study recommends regulating carbon emissions to prolong life expectancy, which is crucial for economic growth. Saidmatov et al. (2024) analyzed the relationships between life expectancy and factors like CO₂ emissions, health spending, GDP, water use, agricultural productivity, and energy consumption in the Aral Sea basin, an environmentally disastrous region. Using various econometric techniques and data from 2002 to 2020, the study found that life expectancy is positively impacted by health spending, GDP, water productivity, agricultural output, energy consumption, and human capital, but negatively impacted by CO₂ emissions. The study emphasizes the need for comprehensive policies considering these factors to ensure longevity. Qehaja et al. (2022) investigated the effect of government expenditure on health and other factors such as health insurance, longevity, average age, and death rate on economic growth in Western Balkan countries. This region includes diverse countries at different development stages with varying government health expenditures. The study found that countries with higher government health expenditures tend to have higher economic growth levels. Investment in healthcare can result in a greater supply of health incentives, enhancing human capital, productivity, and economic performance. Rahim & Muzaffar (2024) aimed to determine how public health spending and financial development affect health outcomes in Pakistan. The findings show that these factors impact health outcomes both temporarily and permanently. The study suggests that increasing public health spending is crucial, but attention should also be focused on lowering healthcare costs, especially for those who cannot afford it. Additionally, the government should provide more domestic credit to citizens to enable them to afford better lifestyles. The study emphasizes the importance of supporting female writers, as literate mothers are better able to understand the world and have more job opportunities, potentially working more productively than men.

2.2 Impact of education and physicians on Life Expectancy

There are several ways in which education and the presence of medical professionals affect life expectancy. Numerous studies have shown that higher education levels are positively correlated with longer life expectancy. Similarly, areas with higher physician-to-population ratios generally experience longer life expectancies due to easier access to high-quality medical treatment. Education contributes to better health literacy and empowerment, enabling people to make informed decisions about their health. It fosters a health-conscious culture within communities, reducing the prevalence of chronic diseases and encouraging healthier lifestyles. Medical professionals, particularly physicians, directly improve health outcomes through their expertise and interventions. Their ability to diagnose and treat diseases, provide preventive care, and manage chronic conditions significantly enhances life expectancy. Communities with adequate physician coverage see lower rates of preventable deaths and better overall health outcomes. Nasreen et al. (2023) investigated the effect of income per capita, air pollution, and healthcare services on health expenditure in Asian economies using annual data from 1995 to 2018. The study found that the availability of clean drinking water and education positively affects health expenditure, while the number of physicians per capita has a negative and considerable impact. Additionally, technology advancement and out-of-pocket spending are positively related to health spending. The study's conclusions provide policymakers with crucial information for creating a more effective healthcare system in Asian nations. Azam et al. (2023) examined the factors affecting life expectancy in Pakistan from 1975 to 2020, focusing on the impact of environmental degradation as indicated by carbon emissions (CO₂ emissions). Long-term estimates suggest that life expectancy is positively impacted by per capita income, urbanization, population growth, birth rate, health spending, and education. Conversely, life expectancy is negatively impacted by CO₂ emissions, the inflation rate, the food production index, and the death rate. The study suggests that regulating carbon emissions is crucial to prolong life expectancy, which is a key determinant of economic growth. Uddin et al. (2023) revisited the socioeconomic factors determining life expectancy, focusing on institutional quality, financial development, and environmental degradation proxied by carbon emissions and the ecological footprint in selected Asian countries, namely Bangladesh, Bhutan, India, Nepal, Pakistan, and Sri Lanka, from 2002 to 2020. The study recommends strengthening the financial sector, increasing healthcare spending, adopting clean and green technologies, and implementing strict environmental pollution regulatory policies to improve life expectancy and general human well-being, ultimately achieving the goals of sustainable development. Montez & Bisesti (2024) investigated the relationship

between educational attainment levels and adult health and longevity in the United States. The study found that higher education levels have become increasingly correlated with better health and longevity outcomes since the 1980s. Higher educated adults have experienced positive health and longevity trends, while lower educated adults have faced negative or stagnant trends. The study suggests reevaluating which educational groups should be considered normative when analyzing trends and paying more attention to the factors and individuals significantly influencing these trends. You & Donnelly (2022) extracted ecological data from United Nations agencies for 215 populations to examine the effects of economic affluence, urban advantages, and obesity on life expectancy at birth (LEB). The study found that physician density has the greatest influence on LEB, followed by economic affluence. Physician density is a major independent contributor to LEB globally, especially in the developing world. The study suggests telehealth as an alternative to increase physicians' capacity and recommends funding to increase physician employment. Ali & Majeed (2023) investigated the impact of globalization and its three dimensions (economic, political, and social) on health using global panel data from 193 countries for the period 1971-2018. The results indicated that globalization and its three dimensions positively impact health, even when controlling for population growth, physician availability, and age dependency. You et al. (2023) highlighted that the contribution of nursing is secondary to that of physicians in the overall population health of 215 countries, using GDP PPP as a measure. The study found that nurses often work under the direction of physicians due to a lack of autonomy. The study suggests that without addressing this issue, health services will continue to perpetuate the invisibility of nursing healthcare from one generation of nurses to another.

2.3 Impact of Fossil Fuel Emission and Carbon Dioxide Emission on Life Expectancy

Studies have demonstrated a clear link between shorter life expectancy and exposure to pollutants from fossil fuels, especially in urban areas with heavy traffic or industrial activity. Harmful gases and small particulate matter released from fossil fuels can deeply enter the lungs, causing respiratory and cardiovascular issues. Furthermore, the broader consequences of carbon dioxide emissions on climate change have significant indirect health implications. Variations in temperature and meteorological conditions can promote the transmission of vector-borne diseases like dengue fever and malaria. Extreme weather events and heatwaves put vulnerable groups, such as the elderly and people with underlying medical conditions, at imminent risk. Sial et al. (2022) assessed the impact of fossil fuel energy consumption on the infant mortality rate in 15 Asian economies from 1996 to 2019. In nations already facing pollution issues, fossil fuel energy consumption is deteriorating living standards. Even if the current infrastructure makes the production of fossil fuel energy viable, it still pollutes the environment. The study used infant mortality rate as a measure of living standards, with employment, gross capital formation, and pre-primary education as independent variables in a non-linear fossil fuel energy consumption model. The impacts were assessed using the feasible generalized least squares method. The study concluded that the U-shaped relationship between fossil fuel energy use and infant mortality indicates that excessive fossil fuel consumption negatively affects living standards, particularly given the poor air quality in Asian economies. Ibrahim Rizwan (2022) probed how income mediates the relationship between fossil fuels and carbon emissions to promote life expectancy in selected oil-abundant African economies from 1980 to 2019. The findings reveal that fossil fuels and carbon emissions reduce life expectancy. However, higher income levels promote healthy life expectancy while mitigating the negative impacts of fossil fuels. Additionally, the study empirically confirms the life-improving roles of human capital. Based on these findings, the study recommends withdrawing subsidies on fossil fuels and making aggregate income more inclusive as key policy measures. Abbas et al. (2024) used life expectancy at birth as a proxy for health well-being, with carbon dioxide emissions (CO₂) and gross domestic product per capita (GDPpc) as independent variables from 1965 to 2020, and current health expenditures per capita (CHE) as a moderator variable from 2000 to 2020. The study concludes that the Pakistani government should adopt effective fiscal and administrative policies from China to better implement health well-being measures and achieve the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Momoh et al. (2024) investigated the effect of economic welfare on life expectancy in sub-Saharan Africa using a panel dataset of 44 selected countries spanning from 2000 to 2021. The study decomposed economic welfare into real gross domestic product, carbon dioxide emissions, and secondary school enrollment rate. The findings suggest that policy reforms aimed at reducing carbon dioxide emissions, increasing income levels, and adequately investing in education should be adopted to achieve longer life expectancy. Bruchon et al. (2024) examined individual preferences for reducing life-cycle CO₂ emissions in vehicle purchase decisions through a stated choice experiment among citizens in Germany. Participants chose between three types of electric vehicles and one conventional vehicle, each characterized by several attributes. The study found that environmental awareness and ecological policy identification did not significantly affect the reduction of CO₂ emissions. Instead, citizens with a strong environmental identity tended to avoid purchasing conventional vehicles. The study discusses several practical policy implications based on these findings. Kanberger et al. (2024) explored the long-standing economic practicality of fossil fuels and their environmental impact. Despite innovations and breakthroughs in the extraction, refining, and combustion of fossil fuels that have reduced their environmental impact, the damage persists. The study concluded that environmental awareness and ecological policy identification have no significant effects on reducing CO₂ emissions. However, citizens with a strong environmental identity tend to avoid purchasing conventional vehicles. The study discusses several practical policy implications related to these findings.

3. METHODOLOGY

Table 1 shows the list of variables for ready reference. Renowned experts and researchers frequently identify intellectual capital as a pivotal source of a company's competitive advantage. This table provides a clear overview of the variables, their symbols, units, and the theoretical expectations regarding their effects on life expectancy. Life expectancy is measured in years, and the theoretical expectation is that as the independent variables change, life expectancy will also change in a positive direction. GDP represents the economic wealth of a country per person. The expectation is that higher GDP per capita positively affects life expectancy. FFEMI measures the percentage of total energy consumption derived from fossil fuels. The expectation is that higher reliance on fossil fuels

negatively impacts life expectancy due to associated environmental and health effects. CO2 emissions per capita is considered a proxy for environmental pollution. The expectation is that higher CO2 emissions have a negative impact on life expectancy due to air pollution and climate change effects. Edu represents the cumulative percentage of the population with a certain level of education. Higher educational attainment is expected to positively influence life expectancy through various pathways such as improved health knowledge and behavior. Current health expenditure as a percentage of GDP reflects the investment a country makes in its healthcare system. Higher health expenditure is expected to positively impact life expectancy through better access to healthcare services and infrastructure.

Table 1: Variables and their Measurements

Variables	Symbols	unit	Theoretical expectations
Life Expectancy	LE	Years	----
Independent Variables			
Gross domestic product per capita	GDP	US\$	positive
Fossil Fuel Energy consumption	FFEMI	% of total	negative
Co2 emission	CO2EMI	Metric tons per capita	negative
Educational Attainment	EDU	Total (%) (cumulative)	positive
Current Health Expenditure	HE	% of GDP	positive
Physicians	PHY	Per 1000 people	positive

Source: World Bank (2023).

A time series is said to be stationary when its statistical properties are constant and there is no seasonality in the data. In a stationary time series, the statistical properties of the data points remain consistent over time and do not depend on the time at which they are observed. This consistency means that the relationships and patterns observed in the data are reliable and can be used to make accurate forecasts. In a non-stationary time series, the statistical properties change over time, often exhibiting trends and seasonal patterns. These fluctuations make it challenging to draw reliable inferences or make accurate forecasts. Since the data characteristics are inconsistent, any model or analysis based on a non-stationary time series may yield unreliable results. A unit root test is a statistical technique used in econometrics to determine if a time series dataset has a unit root, indicating non-stationarity. A unit root implies that a variable lacks long-term stability or trend, as it is influenced by random shocks and does not revert to its mean over time. This test helps identify if differencing is necessary to achieve stationarity for accurate analysis and forecasting.

The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test is a reliable statistical method used to test for a unit root in a time series, determining whether it is non-stationary. It extends the Dickey-Fuller test by including lags of the dependent variable's differences to capture more complex dynamics. A trend and intercept can also be optionally included. The standard equation for the ADF test when an intercept and trend are present is:

$$\Delta Y_t = \alpha + \beta Y_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^p \gamma_i \Delta Y_{t-i} + \epsilon_t$$

Equations with Intercept Only

- I. LE: $\Delta LE = \alpha + \gamma LE_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^p \delta_i \Delta LE_{t-1} + \epsilon_t$
- II. CO2EMI: $\Delta CO2EMI = \alpha + \gamma CO2EMI_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^p \delta_i \Delta CO2EMI_{t-1} + \epsilon_t$
- III. GDP: $\Delta GDP = \alpha + \gamma GDP_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^p \delta_i \Delta GDP_{t-1} + \epsilon_t$
- IV. FFEMI: $\Delta FFEMI = \alpha + \gamma FFEMI_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^p \delta_i \Delta FFEMI_{t-1} + \epsilon_t$
- V. HEXP: $\Delta HEXP = \alpha + \gamma HEXP_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^p \delta_i \Delta HEXP_{t-1} + \epsilon_t$
- VI. PHY: $\Delta PHY = \alpha + \gamma PHY_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^p \delta_i \Delta PHY_{t-1} + \epsilon_t$
- VII. EDU: $\Delta EDU = \alpha + \gamma EDU_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^p \delta_i \Delta EDU_{t-1} + \epsilon_t$

One statistical characteristic of a group of time series variables that show a consistent, long-term association even while they are separately non-stationary is called cointegration. This occurs when a linear combination of these non-stationary variables produces a stationary series. The concept of cointegration is crucial in econometrics and finance because it indicates that the variables share a common stochastic trend and eventually return to equilibrium. Testing for cointegration is essential for modeling long-term interactions between economic variables, such as the relationship between interest rates and investment or import prices and exchange rates.

The Johansen cointegration test is an econometric technique used to determine if multiple non-stationary time series variables share a long-term equilibrium relationship. Unlike the Engle-Granger test, the Johansen test can handle multiple time series simultaneously, making it ideal for complex systems where variables are expected to move together over time. This capability gives it an advantage in analyzing intricate relationships among variables. An analytical statistical model used in econometrics to examine dynamic interactions among variables across time is the Autoregressive Distributed Lag. ARDL models can be applied regardless of whether the underlying variables are strictly stationary since they can capture both the short- and long-term effects of variables on one another. Small sample sizes can be used with them, and they are also rather easy to estimate. The mathematical representation of an Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model can be expressed as follows:

$$\Delta LE_t = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^{p-1} \alpha_1 \Delta LE_{t-i} + \sum_{j=0}^{q1-1} \alpha_2 \Delta CO2EMI_{t-j} + \sum_{k=0}^{q2-1} \alpha_3 \Delta GDP_{t-k} + \sum_{l=0}^{q3-1} \alpha_4 \Delta FFEMI_{t-l} + \sum_{m=0}^{q4-1} \alpha_5 \Delta HEXP_{t-m} + \sum_{n=0}^{q5-1} \alpha_6 \Delta PHY_{t-n} + \sum_{o=0}^{q6-1} \alpha_2 \Delta EDU_{t-o} + \gamma EC_{t-1} + \epsilon t$$

Robust least squares is a regression analysis technique used to minimize the impact of outliers and obtain more accurate parameter estimates when data contains anomalies. Unlike the traditional least squares method, which minimizes the sum of squared residuals, robust least squares employ weighting systems or alternative norms to reduce the influence of large residuals. This adjustment makes the method more resilient to outliers, leading to more reliable results in the presence of anomalous data points. M-estimation in robust regression modifies the least square’s objective function to minimize the impact of outliers by applying a robust loss function, $\rho(r)$, to the residuals. The goal of this approach is to reduce the influence of high residuals compared to the squared loss used in ordinary least squares. Commonly used loss functions for $\rho(r)$ include the Huber and Tukey biweight functions, as they are effective in mitigating the effects of large residuals. S-estimation, which focuses on scale estimation, seeks to produce precise regression parameter estimates with a high breakdown point. The goal of the objective function is to minimize the residuals’ magnitude while ensuring a satisfactory fit. Here, the scale parameter is denoted as s , the residuals are represented by r_i and δ is a constant typically determined by selecting ρ . MM-estimation merges the concepts of M-estimation and S-estimation to deliver highly efficient and robust estimates that withstand outliers. Initially, an S-estimator is employed to obtain accurate scale and location estimates. This two-step process ensures that the estimates are efficient and robust, nearing the maximum likelihood estimates under normal error conditions. By handling outliers distinctively, these estimation strategies aim to offer more reliable statistical analysis even in the presence of anomalous data. A fundamental concept in time series analysis, the impulse response function (IRF) describes how a dynamic system responds over time to external shocks. In a Vector Autoregression (VAR) model, the IRF measures the effect of a single shock to a variable on the present and future values of the endogenous variables. The IRF provides insights into the "paths" that these variables follow after the shock. It is computed as the derivative of the predicted future values of X_t with respect to the shock ϵ_t that occurred immediately. Essentially, it tracks the trajectory of a unit shock in a single variable throughout the system, aiding in the understanding of the dynamics and stability of financial and economic models. Variance Decomposition Analysis is a technique used in time series data analysis to determine the proportion of forecast error variance for each variable in a Vector Autoregression (VAR) model that can be attributed to shocks to that variable itself, as opposed to shocks to other variables in the model. This method helps to clarify how the variables in a multivariate system interact and behave, providing insight into the relative importance and impact of each variable’s shocks within the system.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2 provides descriptive statistics for several variables related to life expectancy, the dependent variable. On average, life expectancy is 63.31 years. Education has a mean of 5.23 years, suggesting that higher education levels likely have a positive impact on life expectancy. CO2 emissions average 0.70 units, with higher emissions potentially negatively affecting life expectancy due to environmental health impacts.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

Description	LIFEXP	EDU	CO2EMI	FFEMI	GDP	HEXP	PHY
Mean	63.31167	5.225856	0.700934	58.95198	914.7971	2.652293	0.724848
Median	63.73100	3.916740	0.710994	59.68739	909.0324	2.749351	0.721000
Maximum	66.75600	8.753310	0.918473	62.47639	1620.743	2.953904	1.084000
Minimum	59.87800	3.174330	0.505906	52.30527	346.6685	2.140169	0.462000
Std. Dev.	2.319610	1.861977	0.102669	2.870981	435.7067	0.217467	0.193579
Skewness	-0.125480	0.869703	0.023164	-0.846204	0.172584	-0.777132	0.538157
Kurtosis	1.633517	2.137125	2.288627	2.692067	1.556023	2.709714	2.195736

Source: Author’s estimation.

Fossil fuel emissions average 58.95 units, and similar to CO2 emissions, higher values might negatively impact life expectancy. GDP averages 914.80 units, and higher GDP generally contributes positively to life expectancy by enabling better healthcare and living standards. Health expenditure averages 2.65 units, with higher spending likely positively affecting life expectancy through improved healthcare services. The number of physicians averages 0.72 units, with higher levels potentially contributing positively to life expectancy by promoting better health. Table 3 shows the correlation estimates.

Table 3: Correlation Estimates

Correlation	LIFEXP	CO2EMI	EDU	FFEMI	GDP	HEXP	PHY
Probability							
LIFEXP	1						

CO2EMI	0.912923	1					

Correlation	LIFEXP	CO2EMI	EDU	FFEMI	GDP	HEXP	PHY
Probability							
	0	-----					
EDU	0.542331	0.509234	1				
	0.0011	0.0025	-----				
FFEMI	0.881634	0.928109	0.498894	1			
	0	0	0.0031	-----			
GDP	0.972071	0.918507	0.561154	0.841707	1		
	0	0	0.0007	0	-----		
HEXP	-0.09183	0.076126	-0.47956	-0.06975	-0.0467	1	
	0.6113	0.6737	0.0047	0.6997	0.7964	-----	
PHY	0.946497	0.894877	0.37381	0.818628	0.948642	0.116929	1
	0	0	0.0321	0	0	0.517	-----

Table 3 presents the correlation coefficients between life expectancy and various independent variables, along with their probability values. Life expectancy exhibits a strong positive correlation with GDP (0.972071), indicating that better economic performance significantly enhances life expectancy. There are also positive correlations with the number of physicians (0.946497), fossil fuel emissions (0.881634), and CO2 emissions (0.912923), suggesting these factors are associated with increased life expectancy. The positive correlation with emissions likely reflects industrial development rather than direct health benefits. Education shows a moderate positive correlation (0.542331), underscoring its positive impact on life expectancy. Conversely, health expenditure has a slight negative correlation (-0.091825), suggesting that higher health spending does not necessarily lead to increased life expectancy. This could be due to inefficiencies or other unaccounted factors in the data. Table 4 shows the unit root estimates.

Table 4: Unit Root Estimates

Variables	LEVEL		FIRST DIFFERENCE		Decision
	Intercept	Intercept & Trend	Intercept	Intercept & Trend	
LIFEXP	-0.7318	-1.9230	-6.1592	-6.0926	I(1)
	0.8244	0.6193	0	0.0001	
GDP	-0.1862	-3.2265	-5.6877	-5.5826	I(1)
	0.93	0.0979	0.0001	0.0004	
FFEMI	-2.1899	-1.8935	-4.9538	-5.3650	I(1)
	0.2136	0.6345	0.0004	0.0007	
CO2EMI	-1.5953	-4.7150	-4.6425	-4.4154	I(0)
	0.4733	0.0043	0.0013	0.01	
EDU	-1.7195	-1.5717	-6.0073	-6.0149	I(1)
	0.4122	0.7818	0	0.0001	
HEXP	-2.3505	-1.5239	-4.3416	-4.3636	I(1)
	0.1635	0.7999	0.0018	0.0083	
PHY	0.6248	-1.8767	-6.2009	-6.4216	I(I)
	0.9882	0.643	0	0	

Table 4 presents the results of the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test, which checks for the presence of unit roots in the variables to determine if they are stationary. The results are shown for both the level and the first difference of each variable, with and without intercept and trend. Life expectancy is found to be stationary at the first difference, indicating it is integrated of order one, I(1). GDP, fossil fuel emissions, education, health expenditure, and the number of physicians are also I(1), meaning they become stationary after first differencing. In contrast, CO2 emissions are stationary at the level, indicating they are I(0). This implies that most variables require differencing to achieve stationarity, except for CO2 emissions. The stationarity of life expectancy after differencing suggests that its fluctuations become predictable over time. Variables like GDP and education, having long-term impacts, stabilize once trends and intercepts are accounted for. Table 5 presents the results of various lag length selection criteria for determining the optimal number of lags in a time series model. The criteria include LogL (log-likelihood), LR (likelihood ratio), FPE (final prediction error), AIC (Akaike information criterion), SC (Schwarz criterion), and HQ (Hannan-Quinn criterion). Each row corresponds to a different lag length (0, 1, and 2). The optimal lag length is identified by the lowest values of the criteria: FPE, AIC, SC, and HQ.

Table 5: Lag Length Selection Criteria

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-221.9292	NA	0.006125	14.76962	15.09343	14.87518
1	-45.14231	262.3289	1.75e-06	6.525310	9.115739	7.369725
2	54.90363	103.2732*	1.11e-07*	3.232024*	8.089077*	4.815302*

The second lag (Lag 2) is preferred as it has the lowest values for FPE (1.11e-07), AIC (3.232024), SC (8.089077), and HQ (4.815302), as indicated by asterisks (*). This suggests that using two lags will provide the best model fit for predicting life expectancy, incorporating past information more effectively and improving the accuracy of the model's predictions. Table 6 shows the pantula test for cointegration.

Table 6: Pantula Test Estimates

Data Trend	None	None	Linear	Linear	Quadratic
	No Intercept	Intercept	Intercept	Intercept	Intercept
Test Type	No Trend	No Trend	No Trend	Trend	Trend
Trace	3	3	1	2	2
Max-Eig	1	1	1	0	2

The results suggest that the number of cointegrating relationships varies depending on the trend and test type, affecting the long-term equilibrium relationships among the variables. For life expectancy, the presence of cointegration indicates that, despite short-term fluctuations, there are stable long-term relationships with the independent variables, which impact life expectancy positively or negatively over time. For example, a linear trend with no intercept and one cointegrating equation indicates a simpler, more stable long-term relationship. In contrast, a quadratic trend with two cointegrating equations suggests greater complexity in the relationships influencing life expectancy. This means that while some trends and equations indicate straightforward, stable relationships, others reveal more intricate interactions that influence life expectancy over the long term. Table 7 shows the Johanson cointegration test estimates.

Table 7: Johanson Cointegration Test Estimates

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace)

Hypothesized		Trace	0.05	
No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Statistic	Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.323781	162.1192	139.2753	0.0012
At most 1 *	0.287097	111.6494	107.3466	0.0253
At most 2	0.215422	67.99458	79.34145	0.2626
At most 3	0.101099	36.69802	55.24578	0.6849
At most 4	0.090960	22.94892	35.01090	0.5121
At most 5	0.050151	10.64662	18.39771	0.4202
At most 6 *	0.030602	4.009284	3.841466	0.0452

Trace test indicates 2 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Maximum Eigenvalue)

Hypothesized		Max-Eigen	0.05	
No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Statistic	Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.323781	50.46982	49.58633	0.0404
At most 1 *	0.287097	43.65482	43.41977	0.0471
At most 2	0.215422	31.29657	37.16359	0.2025
At most 3	0.101099	13.74909	30.81507	0.9492
At most 4	0.090960	12.30231	24.25202	0.7391
At most 5	0.050151	6.637331	17.14769	0.7519
At most 6 *	0.030602	4.009284	3.841466	0.0452

The Johansen Cointegration Test table shows that there are two cointegrating equations among the variables at the 0.05 significance level, based on both the Trace test and the Maximum Eigenvalue test. This indicates stable long-term relationships between life expectancy and the independent variables. Positive impacts on life expectancy could come from variables such as GDP, *POLITICA*, 2(1), 83-99 (2024)

education, and the number of physicians, as these factors tend to improve health and living standards over time. Conversely, negative impacts could be associated with higher CO₂ and fossil fuel emissions, which can deteriorate health and environmental conditions. The presence of cointegration signifies that these relationships are robust and persist over the long term, despite any short-term variations. Table 8 shows the ECM short-run estimates for ARDL approach.

Table 8: ECM Short Run Analysis

ECM Regression				
Case 2: Restricted Constant and No Trend				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(PHY)	2.520588	0.866947	2.907432	0.0043
D(GDP)	0.001167	0.000323	3.611417	0.0004
D(EDU)	0.060793	0.026878	2.261849	0.0255
CointEq(-1)*	-0.068720	0.020087	-3.421127	0.0009
R-squared	0.223519	Mean dependent var		0.046046
Adjusted R-squared	0.205177	S.D. dependent var		0.181306
S.E. of regression	0.161639	Akaike info criterion		-0.776841
Sum squared resid	3.318159	Schwarz criterion		-0.689049
Log likelihood	54.88311	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-0.741167
Durbin-Watson stat	2.043550			

* p-value incompatible with t-Bounds distribution.

Table 8 presents the results of the Error Correction Model (ECM) short-run analysis for life expectancy. The availability of physicians has a positive coefficient (2.520588) and is statistically significant ($p=0.0043$), indicating that increases in the number of physicians positively impact life expectancy in the short run. Economic growth also shows a positive and significant impact (coefficient = 0.001167, $p=0.0004$), suggesting that increases in GDP positively affect life expectancy. Similarly, educational attainment has a positive and significant coefficient (0.060793, $p=0.0255$), indicating that improvements in education lead to higher life expectancy. The error correction term confirms that deviations from the long-term equilibrium are corrected over time, reinforcing the long-term relationship between the variables and life expectancy. The R-squared value is 0.223519, indicating that about 22.35% of the variance in life expectancy is explained by the model in the short run. Overall, the positive impacts of the number of physicians, GDP, and education suggest that improvements in these areas lead to increases in life expectancy. The error correction term ensures that the system returns to equilibrium after short-term fluctuations, highlighting the robustness of the long-term relationships between these variables and life expectancy. The results are linked with the previous studies of (Akinkugbe, & Mohanoe 2009; (Qadir & Majeed et al 2018) and (Akinkugbe, & Mohanoe 2009) The findings from the Error Correction Model (ECM) analysis on the relationship between public expenditure on healthcare and health status in Lesotho can be coherently linked with the ECM results which examined the short-run influences of physician availability, GDP, and education on life expectancy. Both studies utilize the ECM to address how specific variables impact health outcomes, though they focus on different regions and sets of determinants. In the Lesotho study, the inclusion of female literacy and child immunization alongside public expenditure on health and physician availability underscores the multifaceted determinants of health outcomes. This complements the earlier ECM analysis, where the availability of physicians and GDP were significant predictors of life expectancy. In both cases, healthcare access, represented by physician availability, is crucial. However, the Lesotho study introduces additional variables like female literacy and child immunization, which have been found to significantly impact health status. This aligns with the positive effect of educational attainment observed in the earlier analysis, suggesting that broader educational improvements could similarly enhance health outcomes. Interestingly, the Lesotho study finds that income per capita, contrary to many earlier findings, does not significantly affect health status. This contrasts with the previous ECM results where GDP growth, a proxy for economic performance, was a significant determinant of life expectancy. This discrepancy may indicate that economic gains do not uniformly translate to health improvements across different contexts, or that the direct effects of GDP growth on health might be mediated by other factors such as healthcare spending and educational improvements. Overall, linking these ECM analyses highlights the importance of a comprehensive approach to public health policy that includes not only direct healthcare spending but also investments in social determinants of health such as education and preventive care. Such strategies are likely to be more effective in improving health outcomes over the long term, as suggested by the error correction terms in both studies, which indicate that systems tend to return to equilibrium following deviations, underscoring the enduring impact of these investments on health status (Rahim & Muzaffar 2024). The results from the study investigating the impact of public health expenditure and financial development on health outcomes in Pakistan can be cohesively linked to the findings from the earlier ECM analysis regarding life expectancy. Both studies employ the Error Correction Model (ECM) to explore the short-run and long-run relationships between health outcomes and various socio-economic factors. In the Pakistan study, public health expenditure and financial development, measured by domestic credit to the private sector relative to GDP, are shown to have an inverse and significant relationship with life expectancy, infant mortality, and under-five mortality rates. This indicates that increases in public health spending and financial development lead to improvements in these health outcomes, with both factors contributing to a quicker

adjustment towards long-term equilibrium. The use of the ECM highlights that any deviations from the equilibrium state are promptly corrected, showcasing the effectiveness of these investments in improving health outcomes over time. This aligns well with the ECM results from the previous study, where the availability of physicians, GDP growth, and educational attainment all showed positive and significant impacts on life expectancy. In both cases, the ECM plays a critical role in demonstrating how health outcomes adjust to changes in these key determinants over time. The positive coefficients for physicians, GDP, and education in the earlier analysis complement the findings from the Pakistan study, as they collectively emphasize the broad spectrum of economic and health-related variables that can foster better health outcomes. The error correction term in both studies confirms that health outcomes tend to return to a long-term equilibrium following short-term disturbances, reinforcing the stable and significant long-term relationships between the health outcomes and their respective determinants. This consistency in ECM results across different contexts underlines the robustness of the error correction mechanism in capturing the dynamics of how health outcomes respond to changes in economic conditions and public health interventions. Overall, these linked findings from both ECM analyses suggest that strategic increases in public health expenditure, financial development, and socio-economic factors such as the availability of healthcare providers, economic growth, and education not only have direct positive effects on health outcomes but also contribute to the stability of these improvements over time. These insights are particularly valuable for policymakers aiming to enhance health outcomes through targeted economic and health policies, highlighting the importance of maintaining sustained investments in health and economic development to achieve long-term public health goals. Table 9 shows the ARDL long-run estimates.

Table 9: ARDL Long Run Form and Bounds Test

ARDL Long Run Form and Bounds Test

Dependent Variable: D(LIFEXP)

Selected Model: ARDL(1, 1, 0, 1, 0, 1, 0)

Conditional Error Correction Regression

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	2.578431	2.089375	1.234068	0.2196
LIFEXP(-1)*	-0.068720	0.038253	-1.796471	0.0749
PHY(-1)	-0.085302	0.391586	-0.217837	0.8279
HEXP**	0.054500	0.108297	0.503243	0.6157
GDP(-1)	0.000240	0.000206	1.162952	0.2472
FFEMI**	0.026337	0.017493	1.505563	0.1348
EDU(-1)	0.010297	0.014239	0.723212	0.4710
CO2EMI**	-0.163876	0.648984	-0.252511	0.8011
D(PHY)	2.520588	0.981280	2.568674	0.0114
D(GDP)	0.001167	0.000360	3.236963	0.0016
D(EDU)	0.060793	0.028559	2.128693	0.0353

The ARDL (Autoregressive Distributed Lag) model and bounds testing approach provide a comprehensive analysis of how various factors impact life expectancy, showing significance at a 0.09 level. This indicates a 9% chance that the observed relationships could occur by chance, which, although higher than the typical 5% threshold, still suggests potential substantive relationships. The model highlights the role of the lagged dependent variable, specifically previous year's life expectancy (LIFEXP(-1)), which shows a negative coefficient of -0.068720. This negative coefficient suggests that any increase in life expectancy from the previous year tends to be followed by a slight decrease the following year, indicating a slow and gradual adjustment toward a long-term equilibrium state. This effect is somewhat significant with a p-value of 0.0749, suggesting modest confidence in this finding. The analysis also underscores the significant positive impact of physician availability on life expectancy. The coefficient of 2.520588 for this variable points to a substantial improvement in life expectancy with an increase in the number of physicians per capita, reflecting the critical role of healthcare access in enhancing public health. The statistical significance of this relationship is strong, with a p-value of 0.0114, reinforcing the importance of healthcare infrastructure in improving life expectancy. Economic growth, measured through indicators like GDP growth, is another significant variable. It has a positive coefficient of 0.001167, indicating that as the economy expands, life expectancy also tends to increase. This relationship is statistically robust with a p-value of 0.0016, highlighting how economic prosperity contributes to better health outcomes by possibly improving access to healthcare services, nutrition, and living conditions. Educational attainment is another key factor, with a positive coefficient of 0.060793. This suggests that higher levels of education in a population contribute positively to increasing life expectancy. The p-value of 0.0353 for this variable points to a statistically significant impact, likely through mechanisms such as better health literacy and healthier lifestyle choices that education fosters. Overall, these variables collectively indicate that while the path to improved life expectancy involves multiple socio-economic factors, the adjustments toward better health outcomes occur gradually. Enhancements in physician availability, economic stability, and education significantly benefit life expectancy, but these benefits unfold slowly over time. The results are linked with the previous studies of (Saad Rehman et al 2022); (Delavari et al 2016); (Azam et al 2003) and (Azam et al 2003). The study complements findings by investigating the impact of various socio-economic and environmental factors on life expectancy in Pakistan from 1975 to 2020, with a particular emphasis on environmental degradation measured by carbon emissions (CO2 emissions). The long-run estimates of the

autoregressive distributive lag (ARDL) model reveal that increases in CO₂ emissions, along with inflation rate, food production index, and death rate, negatively affect life expectancy, suggesting that environmental degradation and economic volatility shorten life spans. Conversely, positive factors such as per capita income, urbanization, population growth, birth rate, health expenditure, and education are found to extend life expectancy, highlighting the multi-faceted influences on health outcomes. In the short run, the ARDL estimates show somewhat different dynamics: positive impacts of food production index, urbanization, birth rate, infant mortality rate, and education on life expectancy are noted. However, inflation, per capita income, population growth rate, death rate, health expenditure, and CO₂ emissions exert negative effects. These variations between short-term and long-term impacts underline the complex interplay between immediate conditions and more sustained trends. Findings also suggest a need for comprehensive management of not only health and economic policies but also environmental strategies to enhance life expectancy. Specifically, regulating carbon emissions could be a crucial step towards not only improving public health but also supporting sustainable economic growth, as healthier populations are foundational to economic development. This aligns with the previously mentioned ARDL analysis, which emphasized the slow yet significant long-term benefits of improving healthcare access, economic conditions, and educational attainment. Together, these studies paint a broad picture of the determinants of life expectancy, stressing the importance of integrated policies that address both immediate needs and long-term challenges. (Delavari et al 2016) study on life expectancy in Iran from 1985 to 2013 offers valuable insights that align well with the findings from the ARDL analysis regarding the long-term influences on life expectancy. Both studies confirm that economic factors like GDP per capita play a crucial role in enhancing life expectancy. The significant positive effect of GDP per capita in the Iranian context ($p=0.003$) resonates with the ARDL results, where economic growth similarly showed a strong positive impact on life expectancy with a coefficient of 0.001167 and a p-value of 0.0016. This consistency across different studies emphasizes the universal benefit of economic stability and growth on health outcomes. Moreover, the positive influence of healthcare access, as indicated by the number of doctors per 10,000 population in Iran ($p=0.036$), mirrors the ARDL findings where physician availability significantly enhanced life expectancy with a positive coefficient of 2.520588. Both studies highlight the critical importance of accessible and adequate healthcare services in improving life expectancy. Additionally, while the Iranian study found non-significant effects of urbanization, CO₂ emissions, and inflation on life expectancy, the ARDL model highlighted a gradual adjustment to long-term equilibrium in life expectancy, without showing significant impacts from other lagged variables. This difference may point to regional or methodological variations in studying these factors' impact on health outcomes. In summary, the Iranian study not only corroborates several findings from the ARDL analysis but also provides a broader perspective on additional factors affecting life expectancy. Together, these studies provide a comprehensive understanding of the multiple dimensions that influence life expectancy, suggesting areas where policy interventions can be particularly effective. (Saad Rehman et al 2022) explored the asymmetric effects of foreign direct investment (FDI) and population health, measured by life expectancy, using the non-linear autoregressive distributed lag (NARDL) approach, provides intriguing findings that can be linked with the earlier results from the ARDL analysis on various determinants of life expectancy. Both studies employ advanced econometric models to uncover long-term relationships among variables affecting life expectancy, but with different focuses on the nature of these relationships. The NARDL analysis underscores that only positive changes in FDI have a bidirectional causality with life expectancy, suggesting that increases in FDI not only predict but are also predicted by improvements in health outcomes. This finding is particularly significant as it highlights the role of positive economic inputs from abroad in enhancing public health. In contrast, the ARDL findings emphasize the broad positive impacts of internal economic factors like GDP growth and the availability of healthcare resources, such as physicians, which consistently improve life expectancy. Both studies hence indicate that economic health, whether influenced by internal growth or external investment, plays a crucial role in shaping public health outcomes. Additionally, the finding that government expenditure on the social sector, particularly in health, directly impacts life expectancy resonates with the ARDL results where economic growth and resource availability, including healthcare, are critical. The NARDL study further expands this understanding by revealing that not only the presence but also the fluctuation in government spending can have significant effects on health, indicating that reductions in health spending could harm life expectancy. This aligns with the ARDL's focus on the slow adjustment to long-run equilibrium, suggesting that sustained investment in health and education is necessary to maintain and improve life expectancy over time. Moreover, the NARDL model's exploration of asymmetric impacts and causality provides a nuanced understanding that economic and policy changes do not uniformly affect health outcomes. This complexity is mirrored in the ARDL study's observation of the gradual adjustments needed for long-term health improvements, highlighting the sensitivity of life expectancy to a range of economic and policy conditions. In conclusion, while the ARDL model provides a foundation for understanding the direct effects of economic growth, healthcare availability, and education on life expectancy, the NARDL study adds depth by examining how variations in these factors, particularly FDI and government expenditure, influence health outcomes asymmetrically. Together, these studies offer a comprehensive view of the economic determinants of life expectancy, underscoring the importance of stable and positive investment in health and economic policies to foster better health outcomes. Table 10 shows the ARDL-Bounds test estimates.

Table 10: F-Bounds Test

F-Bounds Test		Null Hypothesis: No levels relationship		
Test Statistic	Value	Signif.	I(0)	I(1)
			Asymptotic: n=1000	
F-statistic	1.382375	10%	1.99	2.94
K	6	5%	2.27	3.28
		2.50%	2.55	3.61

F-Bounds Test	Null Hypothesis: No levels relationship		
	1%	2.88	3.99

Table 10 presents the results of the F-Bounds Test, which assesses the presence of a long-term level relationship between life expectancy and its independent variables. The F-statistic value is 1.382375. For different significance levels (10%, 5%, 2.5%, and 1%), the table provides critical values for I(0) and I(1) bounds. Since the F-statistic (1.382375) is lower than all critical values at these significance levels (e.g., 1.99 at 10% I(0) and 2.94 at 10% I(1)), we fail to reject the null hypothesis of no levels relationship. This suggests there is no significant long-term relationship between life expectancy and the independent variables in the model. Positive short-run impacts on life expectancy, such as those from GDP and education, do not translate into significant long-term effects according to this test. Similarly, negative impacts, such as those from CO2 emissions, do not show a significant long-term relationship with life expectancy in this context. Figure 1 shows the IRF estimates.

Response to Cholesky One S.D. (d.f. adjusted) Innovations ± 2 S.E.

Figure 1: IRF Estimates

Source: Author's made.

Table 11 shows the VDA estimates. The variance decomposition table illustrates the proportion of the forecast error variance of life expectancy attributable to shocks in itself and other variables over ten periods. Initially, life expectancy's variance is entirely self-explained (100%). Over time, the influence of other variables increases. By the tenth period, shocks to GDP account for 1.93% of the variance, indicating its growing impact. Fossil fuel emissions and CO2 emissions also show increasing influence, explaining 5.74% and 0.93% of the variance, respectively, by the tenth period. Education progressively accounts for more variance, reaching 1.26%. Healthcare expenditure and physicians have minimal impacts, with healthcare expenditure contributing 0.04% and physicians contributing 0.08% by the tenth period. Overall, while life expectancy is initially influenced by its own shocks, the impact of GDP, education, and other variables grows over time, indicating their increasing relevance in explaining variations in life expectancy.

Table 11: VDA Estimates

Variance Decomposition of LIFEXP								
Period	S.E.	LIFEXP	GDP	FFEMI	CO2EMI	EDU	HEXP	PHY
1	0.185986	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	0.24767	99.82531	0.052453	0.000723	0.031738	0.002453	8.82E-05	0.087236

Variance Decomposition of LIFEXP								
Period	S.E.	LIFEXP	GDP	FFEMI	CO2EMI	EDU	HEXP	PHY
3	0.294179	99.57568	0.081138	0.12795	0.085634	0.025725	0.00011	0.103763
4	0.331499	98.95558	0.236398	0.45011	0.164861	0.074457	0.000181	0.118409
5	0.363423	98.00097	0.482795	0.974187	0.258255	0.162675	0.000716	0.120402
6	0.391698	96.77144	0.77138	1.680884	0.360837	0.299271	0.002346	0.113846
7	0.417399	95.31567	1.073132	2.542896	0.474543	0.484568	0.006079	0.103113
8	0.441209	93.67685	1.371617	3.528694	0.604425	0.712876	0.013182	0.09236
9	0.463595	91.89581	1.657776	4.606201	0.756039	0.97446	0.025064	0.084651
10	0.484883	90.0119	1.926281	5.744953	0.934272	1.25766	0.043114	0.081818

5. CONCLUSIONS AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

This study examines the socioeconomic and environmental factors influencing life expectancy in Pakistan. The study found a positive correlation between life expectancy and healthcare spending, the number of doctors, and educational attainment, suggesting that improvements in these areas could lead to better health outcomes. Conversely, life expectancy is negatively affected by carbon dioxide and fossil fuel emissions, highlighting the need for environmental interventions. The interaction of these factors presents a complex yet clear scenario for the multimodal strategy required to increase life expectancy in Pakistan. While socioeconomic progress is crucial, environmental health should not be neglected. Addressing these issues collectively is essential for enhancing the longevity and quality of life of Pakistan's population. This study not only contributes to the existing body of knowledge but also provides guidance for policymakers to adopt a balanced approach that focuses on both socioeconomic development and environmental sustainability to achieve better public health outcomes. Several recommendations for improving health outcomes emerge from the research findings, which underscore the significant impact of socioeconomic and environmental factors on life expectancy in Pakistan.

To improve life expectancy in Pakistan, a phased strategy is essential. In the short term, immediate economic stimulus can be achieved through tax cuts in high-impact sectors like construction. Enforcing stricter emission standards will reduce air pollution and its health impacts. Increasing educational funding in underserved areas can build a foundation for long-term health improvements. Offering incentives for physicians to work in rural areas will address immediate healthcare access disparities, and boosting funding for emergency healthcare services will provide immediate support and save lives. In the medium term, sustaining economic growth through investments in technology and infrastructure is crucial. Transitioning to renewable energy sources will mitigate health issues related to pollution. Revising educational curricula to include comprehensive health education can promote healthier lifestyles. Expanding the number of medical training facilities will produce more healthcare professionals, and enhancing preventive healthcare services will reduce the burden of disease through early detection and intervention. For long-term sustainability, developing policies that promote innovation and high-value industries is essential. Implementing comprehensive strategies for significant reductions in emissions will have a lasting positive impact on health. Ensuring universal access to quality education will empower individuals to make healthier choices. Overhauling the healthcare system to broaden access and improve service quality is necessary, along with committing to long-term healthcare infrastructure investments. These combined efforts will progressively build upon each other, ensuring immediate improvements while laying the groundwork for enduring enhancements in life expectancy.

To enhance life expectancy in Pakistan through GDP per capita growth, short-term strategies should focus on stimulating immediate economic activity by implementing tax incentives for local businesses and foreign investors, particularly in fast-growing sectors like technology and manufacturing. Rapid investment in infrastructure such as roads and public utilities can directly boost employment. Moving into the medium term, the focus should shift to enhancing human capital through significant investments in education and vocational training, creating a more skilled workforce. Additionally, fostering small and medium enterprise development by providing easier access to finance and streamlining regulatory processes is crucial. In the long term, the goal should be to transform the economic structure towards high-value, knowledge-based industries by sustaining investments in higher education and research and development. Fostering a culture of innovation and ensuring economic stability will attract further investments. These combined efforts are aimed at achieving a consistent rise in GDP per capita, which is linked to better public health services and infrastructure, ultimately improving life expectancy.

To address the impact of fossil fuel emissions on life expectancy in Pakistan, short-term initiatives should include enforcing stricter emissions standards for industries and vehicles, complemented by immediate incentives for adopting cleaner technologies. Moving into the medium term, the focus should shift towards expanding public transportation networks to reduce individual vehicle use and encouraging the adoption of energy-efficient practices in homes and businesses. For long-term strategies, the government should prioritize significant investments in renewable energy infrastructure, such as solar and wind power, aiming to drastically reduce the country's reliance on fossil fuels. These policies not only aim to lower fossil fuel emissions but also to improve air quality significantly, thereby enhancing public health and potentially increasing life expectancy across the population. Each phase builds upon the success of the previous, gradually transforming the energy landscape towards sustainability and health-oriented outcomes.

To enhance life expectancy in Pakistan through increased healthcare expenditure, short-term actions should focus on allocating emergency funds to improve infrastructure and equipment in existing healthcare facilities, especially in critical and emergency care. In the medium term, the strategy should shift towards expanding healthcare coverage and accessibility by building more healthcare

facilities in underserved areas and increasing investments in preventive care programs, such as vaccinations and public health awareness campaigns. For the long term, policies should aim at establishing a sustainable healthcare financing model that includes increased government spending, the introduction of universal health coverage, and fostering partnerships with the private sector to ensure comprehensive, continuous, and affordable care for all citizens. These initiatives should be designed to progressively build a robust healthcare system that can improve overall health outcomes and extend life expectancy by ensuring that all segments of the population have access to quality medical care.

To address the impact of CO₂ emissions on life expectancy in Pakistan, short-term policies should focus on implementing stringent regulations on industrial and vehicular emissions, alongside incentivizing the rapid adoption of cleaner technologies and fuels. In the medium term, the government should promote greater use of public transportation and support the transition to renewable energy sources in residential and commercial sectors, reducing the carbon footprint of these areas. For the long term, the aim should be to set ambitious, legally binding CO₂ reduction targets as part of a broader national climate strategy, which would include reforestation projects and incentives for large-scale renewable energy projects like wind farms and solar parks. This staged approach is designed to progressively reduce CO₂ emissions, thus improving air quality and contributing to better health outcomes and increased life expectancy across the population.

To improve life expectancy in Pakistan through enhanced educational initiatives, short-term actions should focus on immediately increasing funding for schools in the most deprived areas, ensuring access to basic educational resources and facilities. In the medium term, efforts should be directed towards revamping the educational curriculum to incorporate health education, environmental awareness, and digital literacy, preparing students to engage with modern challenges effectively. For the long term, the goal should be to achieve universal access to higher education and ongoing professional development, supported by investments in educational infrastructure and technology. This comprehensive approach aims to significantly raise educational standards across the country, equipping citizens with the knowledge and skills necessary to lead healthier lives and contribute to a more robust economy, thereby increasing life expectancy.

To enhance life expectancy in Pakistan by increasing the density of physicians per 1,000 people, short-term measures should include offering incentives such as higher salaries and loan forgiveness to attract physicians to rural and underserved areas. In the medium term, the focus should shift to expanding medical education facilities and increasing enrollment capacities to train more physicians, addressing the current shortage and ensuring a better distribution of healthcare professionals across the country. For the long-term strategy, the government should aim to integrate advanced healthcare technologies like telemedicine into the system, which can extend the reach of fewer physicians and improve healthcare delivery efficiency. These steps are intended to not only increase the number of available healthcare providers but also to enhance the overall quality of medical care, thereby improving health outcomes and increasing life expectancy throughout Pakistan.

Ethical approval

Not Applicable.

Informed consent

The study was conducted with equal participation by all authors.

Conflicts of interests

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interests.

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Data and materials availability

All data associated with this study are present in the paper.

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